

PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PHYSIOLOGICAL THEORIES OF SCIENTISTS ABOUT ATTENTION.

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Anottasiya: The article discusses the psychological and physiological processes of attention and the opinions of scientists who have scientifically proven the psychological and physiological theories of attention.

Key words: theory, physiological, psychological, brain, nerve.

Before giving a description of the person's understanding, it is necessary to emphasize the importance of all psychological and physiological cognitive processes in the development of the individual, as one of the psychologically simple cognitive processes is attention. Attention, along with other mental processes, is associated with certain physiological phenomena. Excitation of some nerve centers and inhibition of others forms the physiological basis of separation of separate stimuli in a certain direction and the course of processes. Sescendent acting on humans produces brain activation mediated by the reticular formation.[1]

Among the "starting" mechanisms of the reticular formation, it is worth mentioning the approximate reflex, which is an innate reaction of human and animal organisms to all changes in the environment. For example, a child who is studying in a quiet room with his thoughts concentrated. Suddenly the door to the room opens. The boy, who is studying hard, involuntarily looks at the door.

The central mechanisms of attention are related to the excitation of the same nerve centers and the inhibition of others. It is at this level that separation of external effects related to the strength of nerve impulses occurs. A strong arousal suppresses a weak arousal that occurred at the same time and determines the course of mental activity in the appropriate direction. But there is also a possibility of joining one or two sescantists that have an effect at the same time and reinforce each other.[2] When talking about the physiological basis of attention, it is worth mentioning two more important phenomena: irradiation of nerve processes and dominance. Ch. Defined by Sherrington and academic I.P. According to the law of induction of neural processes widely used by Pavlov, the excitation that occurs in one area of the cerebral cortex causes the

inhibition of other areas (continuous induction) or alternates with the inhibition of this area of the brain (sequential induction). Levels are easily generated, and new conditional connections are effectively established, as favorable conditions for excitation are created in the area of the cerebral cortex where the irradiation event occurs. And these physiological processes provide attention.

A.A. According to the principle of dominance put forward by Ukhtomsky, it is a temporarily dominant center of excitation in the brain that always determines the activity of nerve centers in a certain time and thus gives a certain direction to human behavior. will be available. Based on the characteristics of dominance, the impulses coming to the nervous system are collected and concentrated, at the same time, the activity of other centers decreases, due to this, the excitation is increased. According to these properties, dominance is a stable focus of arousal, which in turn makes it possible to explain the neural mechanism that strengthens the intensity of attention.[1] Attention is a unique psychological phenomenon, and until now psychologists do not have a single opinion about it. According to some authors, attention cannot be studied as an independent phenomenon, since it is involved in any mental process to one degree or another. Others advocate the independence of attention as a mental process. Modern researchers pay more attention to neurophysiological processes. Changes in bioelectric activity in any area of the brain were found to occur in healthy people under conditions of stress. This activity is associated with the activity of a special type of neurons located in the forehead area. The first type of neurons - "novelty detectors" are activated under the influence of new stimuli and reduce their activity according to the degree of habituation to them. Unlike them, "waiting" neurons are activated only when the organism meets an object capable of satisfying the current need.

Thus, attention is provided by the activity of a whole system of interconnected brain structures. The complex structure of the physiological mechanisms of attention and conflicting views on its nature led to the emergence of a number of psychological theories of attention.

Among the theories of attention, the theory of T. Ribault is widely popular, according to him, attention is always connected with emotions and occurs with their help. According to him, since the intensity and duration of voluntary attention provide the intensity and duration of the emotional state associated with the object of attention, T. Ribeau was able to see a special organic connection between emotions and voluntary attention.[2]

D.N. According to Uznadze, attention is directly connected with inclination. According to him, inclination expresses the state of attention from within. Under the influence of inclination, a certain image or impression formed in the perception of the real environment is separated. This image or impression becomes the object of attention, and the process itself is called objectification.[2] Attention is the focus and concentration of mental activity on something. This is a general definition of animal as well as human attention. Human attention can be studied as the direction and concentration of a person's attention on certain objects, while being distracted from other objects. It follows from this definition that the important features of attention are its direction and concentration.

P.yA. Galperin also proposed an interesting concept of attention. Its concept consists of the following main cases:

1. Attention is one of the situations of directional-research activity and consists of a mental action aimed at the content of an image, thought, other phenomenon existing in the human psyche at a certain time.
2. The main task of attention is control over the mental image, content of action, etc. Every human action has direction, execution and control components. This last part is embodied by attention.
3. In contrast to the activities aimed at the production of a certain product, the activities of control or attention will not have a specific result.
4. Attention, as an independent act, separates only when the movement is in a shortened state, not mental. In this case, any kind of control cannot be learned as attention. Control evaluates the action in general, while attention ensures its improvement.
5. If attention is studied as an activity of mental control, then certain voluntary and involuntary acts of attention are the result of the formation of new mental actions.
6. Voluntary attention is planned attention, which is a form of control performed according to a prearranged plan or pattern.

Despite the existence of a large number of theories, it should be noted that the problem of the theoretical importance of attention has not lost its importance. In conclusion, the debate about the nature of attention continues as before.[1]

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